

Detrital zircon age constraint on the low-grade sedimentary succession along the Mareshnitsa River Valley, eastern Circum-Rhodope Belt, Bulgaria

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Abstract. We focused on the eastern Circum-Rhodope belt (CRB) low-grade sequence along the Mareshnitsa River Valley in Bulgaria. U-Pb detrital zircon geochronology revealed latest Late Jurassic maximum depositional age of a metasandstone. A major Jurassic zircon cluster in the metasandstone is consistent with a provenance from the CRB-related Evros arc, whereas the minor cluster of Triassic zircons come from the high-grade basement. The results indicate mostly latest Late Jurassic sedimentation proximal to the Evros arc (CRB) and minor detrital input from the continental margin of Eurasia (Rhodope). The results further support the presence of Mesozoic (Jurassic) oceanic lithosphere mantle remnants within the metamorphic basement of the eastern Rhodope Massif.

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INTRODUCTION

The Circum-Rhodope Belt (CRB) is a major tectonic unit that surrounds both the Rhodope and the Serbo-Macedonian zones of the Alpine orogen in the northern Aegean region (Fig. 1, inset). Mostly carbonate and shale sedimentary successions, and their Triassic–Jurassic fossil contents, have been used to recognize the Mesozoic age and regionally extensive nature of the CRB across the Aegean Sea (Kauffmann *et al.*, 1976). In the eastern CRB,

exposed in the Thrace area, and eastern Rhodope Massif of Bulgaria and Greece, biostratigraphic (Trikkalinos, 1955; Maratos and Andronopoulos, 1964; Boyanov *et al.*, 1990; Dimadis *et al.*, 1996; Dimadis and Nikolov, 1997) and limited radiometric (Meinhold *et al.*, 2010; Bonev *et al.*, 2019a) age constraints have been used to infer Triassic and Jurassic depositional ages.

In the Bulgarian part of the eastern CRB, the lithological similarity with the two main CRB units in the Thrace area of Greece (see Fig. 1), namely

Fig. 1. Simplified geological map along the MRV (after Sarov *et al.*, 2008). The location of the sample studied for U-Pb geochronology is shown. Inset: Tectonic framework of the Alpine orogen in the northern Aegean region of the eastern Mediterranean region. Box locates the study area.

the Makri and Drimos-Melia units, has been used for the exposed CRB metasedimentary successions (Boyanov *et al.*, 1990). The eastern CRB has been shown to represent a subduction-accretion complex related to the early Alpine tectonic evolution of an intra-oceanic arc system that gave birth to the Jurassic supra-subduction zone Evros ophiolite along the Eurasian plate margin (Bonev and Stampfli, 2008, 2011). However, another small exposure of the CRB along the Mareshnitsa River Valley (MRV) has received little attention despite

the visible geological characteristics that are pertinent to the CRB.

In this contribution, we provide new U-Pb detrital zircon geochronology for the low-grade sedimentary succession along the MRV, which forms part of the eastern CRB in Bulgaria. The aim of this study is to identify temporally the depositional history of the metasedimentary succession that will provide a link to the sedimentation across the Eurasian continental margin towards the Jurassic Evros island arc system.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The largest outcrop area of the eastern CRB in Bulgaria, called the Mesozoic low-grade unit (Bonev and Stampfli, 2003, 2008), the Mandritsa Group (Boyanov *et al.*, 1990), and also the Mandritsa unit (Ricou *et al.*, 1998; Bonev *et al.*, 2010a), laterally continues in northeastern Greece. The second largest and most important area where the Mesozoic low-grade unit is exposed, is the Kulidzhik nappe (Boyanov, 1969), whose allochthon cooled below 350 °C between 157 Ma and 154 Ma as derived from $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ geochronology (Bonev *et al.*, 2010b).

The metasedimentary rocks along the MRV (Fig. 1) were described as an at least 400-m-thick low-grade series of probable Ordovician age (Ivanov, 1961) reaching the grade of biotite-chlorite and sericite-chlorite sub-facies of the greenschist facies metamorphism. The main rock varieties are calc-schist, albite schist and quartz mica-schist. According to Ivanov (1961), the sedimentary protoliths were mostly shale and sandy rocks, whereas rare epidote-actinolite-chlorite schist were derived at the expense of basic tuffs and tuffites. Noteworthy, according to the latter author, is that the metamorphism of the low-grade series was not affected by the intrusion of the adjacent Chuchuliga granite, which was dated at 69 Ma by Marchev *et al.* (2006). In addition, Boyanov *et al.* (1963) also described carbonate schist, greywacke schist and occurrences of ultrabasic rocks along the MRV, and they correlated these lithologies with the low-grade rocks exposed in the Mandritsa area. Sarov *et al.* (2008) also

correlated the low-grade succession exposed along the MRV with the same grade metamorphic succession of the Mandritsa unit. However, the ultrabasic rocks included in the low-grade succession they assigned to the underlying Krumovitsa unit (Sarov *et al.* 2008), which is largely equivalent to the upper high-grade basement unit (Bonev, 2006). Our field data confirmed the occurrence of a low-grade meta-sedimentary series hosting peridotite lenses along the MRV (Fig. 2).

U-Pb GEOCHRONOLOGY

Along the MRV, sample R22 (N41°22'8.2" E25°59'59.9") was collected from a metasandstone overlying quartz mica-schist (see Fig. 1 for location). The medium-grained metasandstone mainly consists of quartz and feldspar and minor white mica. For the U-Pb geochronology, the sample preparation and analytical procedures are the same as described by Bonev *et al.* (2019b).

Zircons from the metasandstone sample R22 show semi-rounded to rounded shapes of visibly prismatic and pyramidal crystals varying in size from 80 μm to 450 μm (av. aspect ratio 1.7), some of which have a homogeneous pattern and others magmatic oscillatory- and sector zoning patterns (Fig. 3a). The $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ ages obtained from 105 analyses range from 668 Ma to 143 Ma (Fig. 3b). In sample R22, from 91 concordant zircons, a series of clusters was established with different density and various ages. The main age cluster of 25 zir-

Fig. 2. Photomicrographs of the low-grade succession and a peridotite along the MRV: a) calc-schist in which white mica and calcite define the greenschist facies foliation; b) mesh texture of peridotite. Mineral abbreviations (after Whitney and Evans, 2010): cal – calcite; qz – quartz; ms – muscovite; sp – spinel; srp – serpentinite.

cons yielded a concordia age of 156.86 ± 0.53 Ma, followed by a cluster of twelve zircons that gave a concordia age of 162.69 ± 1 Ma, and a cluster of nine zircons with a concordia age of 152.8 ± 1.2 Ma. Two pairs of seven concordant zircons cluster at 169.05 ± 0.81 Ma and 201.1 ± 1.6 Ma. Two pairs of six zircons each gave concordant ages at 186.8 ± 1.4 Ma and 234.1 ± 1.5 Ma. Four clusters of three zircons each yielded concordant ages at 175.5 ± 2.5 Ma, 220.3 ± 1.8 Ma, 240.3 ± 1.8 Ma, and 251.6 ± 4.0 Ma. Single zircons yielded concordant ages at 277.5 ± 5.9 Ma, 304.02 ± 3.2 Ma, 541.2 ± 5.8 Ma, 586.3 ± 8.6 Ma, and 667.3 ± 7.0 Ma. The two youngest concordant zircons provided an age of 145.3 ± 1.8 Ma, and hence define a maximum latest Late Jurassic depositional age (Fig. 3c). The Th/U ratios of the dated concordant zircons in this sample range from 0.03 to 0.93, but the majority (>90%) of these ratios are in the 0.11–0.93 range, which is typical for magmatic zircons (e.g., Rubatto, 2002; Tiepel *et al.*, 2004).

DISCUSSION

The MRV metasandstone has a latest Late Jurassic maximum depositional age of 145 Ma (Fig. 3c). The number of dated zircons from the R22 clastic rock sample meets the required amount of statistical criteria (Vermeesch, 2004). Taken collectively, the number of dated zircons from the clastic sample satisfies and exceeds the statistical confidence at the 95% level. Therefore, the latest Late Jurassic detrital zircon record obtained in this study provides an unequivocal depositional age constraint for the clastic rocks along the MRV, which is similar to that obtained for the Mandritsa unit at 144 Ma (Bonev *et al.*, 2019a).

Furthermore, the depositional age of the metasandstone provides a minimum latest Late Jurassic igneous age for the peridotite lenses enclosed in the schist succession along the MRV or tectonic emplacement age of the peridotite within the succession. This temporal constraint for the peridotite along the MRV further supports the presence of Mesozoic (Jurassic) oceanic lithosphere mantle remnants in the high-grade metamorphic basement of the eastern Rhodope Massif (Filipov *et al.*, 2022), but also within the Mesozoic low-grade unit representing the eastern CRB.

The high Th/U ratios of the detrital zircons reflect mostly a magmatic provenance and an additional limited provenance from metamorphic influence. In this direction, the Th/U ratios and the documented age clusters of detrital zircons testify to the same age as the magmatic protoliths of the metamorphic

Fig. 3. (a) Cathodoluminescence image of dated zircons in sample R22. Circles represent the location of spot analyses with corresponding ages given with 2σ error. Green-colored numbers correspond to the youngest population; (b) density distribution diagram of zircons from sample R22; (c) Concordia diagram for the two youngest zircons in sample R22.

basement of the eastern Rhodope Massif, including the eastern CRB (see below).

The detrital zircon age clusters of the studied sample precisely reflect the age of the basement

rocks and the proximity to the Evros island arc system. Particularly, sample R22 reveals a major cluster of Jurassic zircons, which corresponds to the age of the magmatic members of the Evros ophiolite (176–164 Ma, Bonev *et al.*, 2015), as well as of the metagranitoid protoliths in the high-grade metamorphic basement of the eastern Rhodope Massif (151–150 Ma, Cornelius, 2008; 160–154 Ma, Bonev *et al.*, 2015). The same is valid for the minor cluster of Triassic zircons with ages overlapping with those of the Triassic metagranitoids in the high-grade metamorphic basement (Drakoulis *et al.*, 2013). This implies that these Triassic metagranitoids had already been exposed on the surface by Late Jurassic times. Other volumetrically minor zircon clusters and single zircon grains of Carboniferous–Permian age have their age equivalents in Carboniferous–Permian magmatic rocks that built the high-grade metamorphic basement (Peytcheva and Quadt, 1995; Cornelius, 2008; Liati *et al.*, 2011). Single Neoproterozoic zircons also have provenance from the high-grade metamorphic basement of the eastern Rhodope Massif (Bonev *et al.*, 2013a, and references therein). As the major detrital zircon age cluster of the metasandstone overlaps with the ages of the Jurassic Evros ophiolite magmatic rocks, it suggests that the source area was not far from the depositional site proximal to the Evros arc system.

To sum up, the clastic sample from MRV received detrital material mainly from the Evros arc system magmatic rocks. Because the MRV low-grade succession, proximal to an arc system, contains peridotite lenses, this implies its shallow crustal level position in a trench to arc depositional setting.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Detrital zircon U-Pb geochronological data obtained for the clastic rock sample of the eastern CRB reveal deposition in the latest Late Jurassic at 145 Ma. The main Jurassic-aged zircon populations are followed in decreasing abundances by Triassic age clusters, and few Carboniferous and Neoproterozoic zircons. The prominent clusters of Jurassic zircons are sourced from the Jurassic Evros island arc system, whose age of magmatic products is overlapped by the established detrital zircons, together with a minor contribution of detrital material from the high-grade metamorphic basement.

2. As the MRV low-grade schist contains peridotite lenses, the whole metamorphic succession might be located at a shallow level position of a trench to island arc system. A minimum Late Jurassic igneous age is evidenced for the peridotite lenses from the detrital zircon record along the MRV.

3. From a paleotectonic point of view, we interpret the provenance of the Jurassic detrital zircons from the Evros island arc system in the metasandstone sample, whereas the provenance of the Carboniferous–Permian to Jurassic detrital zircons comes from the eastern Rhodope high-grade metamorphic basement. Therefore, we have a record of depositional environment proximal to the Evros island arc system, in which zircons from the continental margin of Eurasia were incorporated within the trench towards the island arc system.

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